

Ecosystem accounting for territorial governance in Small Island Developing States

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Abstract

In the context of accelerating global nature loss, ecosystem extent and condition accounts underpin ecosystem service assessments and their integration into economic and policy decision-making. However, uptake of the SEEA-EA – the UN Ecosystem Accounting framework – has been slow in African countries and Small Island Developing States (SIDS), despite their acute land-use pressures and vulnerability to ecosystem degradation. Using the island of Mauritius as an illustrative case, we develop the first SEEA-EA aligned ecosystem extent and condition accounts for a SIDS, built entirely from open-source geospatial data and designed for replication in data-scarce contexts. Accounts are compiled for 2010 and 2020, with two scenarios modelled for 2050. Results indicate that Mauritius was already highly degraded by 2010, such that subsequent land-cover changes produced only limited shifts in overall condition across the island. Furthermore, restoration scenarios aligned with the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework yield relatively modest improvements in ecosystem condition, highlighting potential tensions between the objectives of the CBD and UNCCD. This study advances both the methodology and empirical application of ecosystem accounting in data-constrained settings, supporting its use in nature-positive governance and development planning.

1. Introduction

1.1. Ecosystem accounting for environmental sustainability

For decades, environmental agendas have been defined at the international level, requiring national responses led by governments, namely through the domestication of global frameworks and the implementation of associated mechanisms (Breuer et al., 2023; Guiry, 2024). In recent years, the climate and biodiversity crises have increasingly been reframed as economic and financial risks, which are material to firms, sovereigns, and financial institutions such as banks and insurers (Calice, Diaz Kalen, Dunz & Miguel, 2023; Gardes-Landolfini et al., 2024; Ranger & Oliver, 2024; Allianz, 2025; Ceglar et al., 2025). The so-called “value at risk” stems from the loss of ecosystem services such as water regulation, food and materials provision, and climate regulation among others, as ecosystems are impacted by climate change, biodiversity loss and their respective drivers, including land use change (Gardes-Landolfini et al., 2024; Ranger, Pasqua & Adam, 2025). Conversely, the notion of ecosystems as investable assets is also gaining ground, aiming to secure their services and associated benefits (Dudley et al., 2025; Ranger, Pasqua & Adam, 2025; Stuchtey and Witter, 2025). These functions are however contingent on ecosystems’ *extent* and *condition* (La Notte, et al., 2022; Martini, et al., 2024; Bedford et al., 2025; Seguin et al., 2026), which is why their measurement is currently seeing significant methodological development to support various risk and asset pricing analytics (Bedford et al., 2025; Rebalance Earth, 2025; Stuchtey and Witter, 2025).

While targeted integration into corporate, financial and economic models continues to be elaborated, assessing ecosystem extent and condition at national level has been institutionalised in the form of the UN System of Environmental Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA-EA), through its adoption as statistical standard in 2021 (Hein, et al., 2020; Edens, et al., 2022). The SEEA-EA seeks to complement national accounts (Comte et al., 2022; Ramihangihajason et al., 2025), with ecosystem accounts being of particular interest to biodiversity policy under the UN Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, 2022), climate change adaptation and mitigation under the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) (Araza et al., 2026), and sustainable land management towards Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN) under the UN Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) (UNCCD/CBD, 2019; UNSD, 2020), including through the biodiversity, climate, water and food nexus (Bateman et al., 2024; IPBES, 2024). Despite years of development and experimental application globally (Edens, et al., 2022; Comte et al., 2022), however, uptake of the framework has been slow. In continental Africa, for instance, only five countries had produced extent accounts by 2024, and only one for condition accounts (UN, 2025); shortcomings attributed to limited data availability and insufficient domestic technical and institutional capacity (UNSC, 2025). Among Small Island Developing States (SIDS),

where land is particularly scarce and highly exposed to anthropic pressures (Deenapanray & Bassi, 2014; Nel, et al., 2021; Thomas and Theokritoff, 2024), not a single country has yet produced either extent or condition accounts (UN, 2025). Finally, beyond the pace of technical adoption, ecosystem accounting has yet to see widespread adoption in environmental and land use policymaking (Virto et al., 2018; Ahlroth et al., 2019; NESC, 2024), as the accounts' complexity can limit engagement by non-specialist policymakers (Díaz et al., 2019; Schneider et al., 2025), who are likely even more scarce than technical staff.

1.2. Research Objectives

Considering the above situation, there is an urgent need to accelerate both technical and policy uptake of ecosystem accounting, for capacity-constrained states to adequately appraise their natural capital in the wider scope of (sustainable) economic development. Today, this can be addressed through abundant open-access data applicable to ecosystem accounting (Gonzalez et al., 2026), but practical, transparent and replicable methodological applications are lacking to support capacity development (see Section 1.3). In addition to accounts by ecosystems or ecosystem types (ET), we argue that clear, aggregated land condition results compared to the pristine state must be produced for the relevant land management policy and decision makers at national and subnational levels, enabling the identification of priority intervention areas, then mandating technical staff to leverage ecosystem-level insights.

The present study responds to these gaps through the first ecosystem extent and condition accounts elaborated for a SIDS, using the island of Mauritius as a paradigmatic case. Small islands offer a unique lens to better understand the complex socio-ecological dynamics linking unsustainable land use changes and environmental degradation, and by extension human wellbeing in the scope of sustainable development (Fernández-Palacios et al. 2021; Ortiz et al. 2023; Koenig et al. 2026). Mauritius encapsulates the challenges shared across SIDS: a small, densely populated island with a complex land-use history, significant biodiversity value, exposure to climate-driven risks, and development ambitions that outpace available environmental data (Koenig and Deenapanray, 2024).

Here, we used open-source geospatial data and a transparent, replicable methodology to assess extent and condition for the dominant terrestrial ecosystems of Mauritius for the years 2010 and 2020. Further, two scenarios for the year 2050 were modelled (King, et al., 2023; Zucca, et al., 2024) based on expected land cover changes and the Kunming Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF) global restoration target (CBD, 2022). We finally propose an aggregated land account deemed to be more directly informative for governance in the scope of sustainable land management and broader nature-positive policy. This application enlightens readily actionable

governance avenues and serves as a foundation for further integration in the island's economic and financial systems.

1.3. Ecosystem extent and condition accounting

Among the SEEA-EA's core accounts, extent accounts provide information on the surface areas covered by different ecosystems. The classification of ecosystems relies on ecosystem typologies, which can be multifarious through different national and international systems (Nicholson Thomas, et al., 2025; Rendón, et al., 2025). To overcome disparities, the SEEA-EA adopts a typology that is based on the Global Ecosystems Typology of the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN-GET) (Keith, et al., 2020). For data sources, the SEEA-EA recommends the use of national data, or when these are not available, global datasets which can be calibrated through ground assessment programmes. In Mauritius, there is no up-to-date map of ecosystem types, nor a typology for classifying them. The most precise global dataset relevant to ecosystem extent and recommended by the SEEA-EA is the 250-meter resolution map of World Terrestrial Ecosystems (Sayre et al., 2020), integrating global temperature domains, global moisture domains, global landforms, and year 2015 global vegetation and land use. In this map, Mauritius features the main landcover/vegetation categories of settlement, cropland, and forest; the landforms of plains, mountains, and tablelands; and only one climate region: subtropical moist, which is not sufficiently accurate for local needs given the island's various microclimates (Cheke and Hume, 2008; Sultan, 2021). We therefore performed a mapping of ecosystems through a downscaled procedure based on Sayre et al. (2020) for this study, as described in Section 4 (Methods).

Ecosystem condition (EC) is aimed at providing a measure of quality by ecosystem type or asset. Condition is expressed through a composite index integrating six recommended ecosystem state characteristics; two abiotic, three biotic, and one landscape state characteristic, which together constitute the SEEA Ecosystem Condition Typology (ECT) (Keith, et al., 2020; Czúcz, et al., 2021; Nicholson Thomas, et al., 2025). This accounting is to reflect local factors, including for the setting of lower- and upper-bound reference values per ecosystem characteristic variable (rescaling) for the creation of condition indicators, and for decisions on indicator weights in the composite condition index (Keith et al., 2020; Czúcz et al., 2021). Where condition accounts have been compiled, however, several have bypassed these steps, presenting condition accounts as opening and closing stocks for variables in their physical units, (Vysna et al., 2021; NBS, 2021; NSO, 2021; Czúcz et al., 2025). In addition, index-based accounts generally focused on a specific ecosystem type (Comte et al., 2022), such as forests (Bruzón, Arrogante-Funes & Santos-Martín, 2023; Maes et al., 2023), or water bodies (IBGE, 2021) in accordance with the SEEA-EA framework, which prescribes

condition accounting for ecosystem assets of various types within Ecosystem Accounting Areas (EAA); typically administrative areas.

In this study, we computed a condition index for the ecosystem types defined in the previous step (accounting for ecosystem extent), as well as an aggregated account relative to a pristine state, deemed to be more directly informative for governance in the scope of sustainable land management and broader nature-positive policy. The results obtained for Mauritius island demonstrate the level of detail attainable for the small geographical extents which characterise SIDS, and the methodology is described for replicability in SIDS and beyond.

2. Results

2.1. Ecosystems extent and condition

In terms of typology, the three dominant landcover classes of the island, namely tree cover, croplands, and built-up areas (Koenig et al., 2024), were first reclassified as ecosystem groups for alignment with the IUCN-GET (Keith, et al., 2020), as shown in Table 1 and described in Section 4.1. Figure 1 displays the baseline map of ecosystem extent for the year 2010 and Figure 2 depicts changes in extent and condition across the ecosystem groups present on Mauritius island for 2010, 2020, and relevant 2050 scenarios, as described in the following sub-sections. Corresponding maps for the years 2020 and 2050 are included in Supplementary Information (Fig S1-S3).

Table 1: Final Ecosystem Typology for Mauritius. Source: Author's elaboration.

LC Type	LC	IUCN-GET EFG	EG	EG Label	Elevation/Landform: Coastal (C), Lowland (L), Intermediate (I), Upland (U), Relief (R)														
					1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4	4	5	5	5
					C	C	C	L	L	L	I	I	I	U	U	U	R	R	R
Tree cover	2	T1.1/T1.2	2	Forests	211	212	213	221	222	223	231	232	233	241	242	243	251	252	253
Crops	4	T7.1/T7.3	4	Croplands	411	412	413	421	422	423	431	432	433	441	442	443	451	452	453
Built area	5	T7.4	5	Urban & industrial ecosystems	511	512	513	521	522	523	531	532	533	541	542	543	551	552	553
Land in development	6	T7.4																	
Transport	7	T7.4																	
Quarries	8	T7.4																	
Solar farms	9	T7.4																	
Grass & shrubs	10	T7.2/T7.5	1	Grass & shrublands	10														
Golf	11	(T7.2)																	
Mangroves	13	MFT1.2	13	Mangroves	13														
Upland marsh	17	TF1.1/TF1.3	17	Upland marsh	17														
Coastal marsh	18	TF1.3	18	Coastal marsh	18														
Rivers	19	F1.1/F1.2/F1.4/ F1.5	29	Rivers	19														
Water bodies	20	F2.2/F2.3/F2.5/ F3.1	20	Water bodies	20														
Sand / Beaches	23	MT1.3	23	Sand / Beaches	23														
					D	M	W	D	M	W	D	M	W	D	M	W	D	M	W
					1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
Climate Regions: Dry (D), Moist (M), Wet (W)																			

The three-digit ecosystem type codes must be read as follows: the first digit represents the EG; the next digit represents the elevation-landform code (1 to 5), and the last represents the climate region (1 to 3). For example, code 223 stands for forest, lowland, wet. In the results section, wherein ecosystem groups are reported on individually, only the last two digits are used.

Legend

Forests	Croplands	Urban	LC Classes
212 - Coastal moist	412 - Coastal moist	511 - Coastal dry	Grass & shrubs
222 - Lowland moist	421 - Lowland dry	512 - Coastal moist	Golf
223 - Lowland wet	422 - Lowland moist	521 - Lowland dry	Mangroves
232 - Int' moist	423 - Lowland wet	522 - Lowland moist	Upland marsh
233 - Int' wet	432 - Int' moist	523 - Lowland wet	Coastal marsh
243 - Upland wet	433 - Int' wet	531 - Int' dry	Rivers
25 - Relief	443 - upland wet	532 - Int' moist	Water bodies
		533 - Int' wet	Beaches and sand
		542 - Upland moist	
		543 - Upland wet	

Int' = Intermediate altitude (200-400m a.s.l.)

Figure 1: Map of terrestrial ecosystems, 2010. Source: Authors' elaboration.

Figure 2: Ecosystem extent (bar charts) and condition (line charts) changes across ecosystem types, grouped by forests (a), agricultural ecosystems (b), and urban & industrial ecosystems (c), in Mauritius for 2010 and 2020. Extent changes only are presented for the applicable 2050 scenarios. “Area 2050” indicates both scenarios for (b) and (c) since those ecosystems are not affected by SC2 changes relative to SC1. Source: Authors’ elaboration.

2.1.1. Extent variations

Extent changes reflect the broader landcover dynamics described by Koenig et al. (2024) and other recent studies (e.g. Mahadea-Nemdharry, et al., 2025), characterised by urban sprawl, contraction of croplands, and a dynamically stable forest stock, i.e. with gains and losses across different forest. At the level of ecosystems, coastal moist, lowland dry, lowland moist and intermediate wet forests made minor gains from 2010 to 2020, whereas upland wet forests experienced small losses. For 2050 under the SC2 scenario, it appears that lowland moist regions held most opportunity for reforestation, owing to the presence of large grass & shrubs patches. This is likely due to their accessibility that had presumably led to their deforestation in the first place. Most agricultural ecosystems have decreased in extent between 2010 and 2020, especially in the lowlands but also in the intermediate wet and upland wet regions (Figure 2b.). These dynamics are set to continue in both 2050 scenarios, albeit to a lesser extent. The opposite trend is noted across urban & industrial ecosystems, particularly in the lowland dry and moist, as well as upland wet regions (Figure 2c.). Interestingly, a reduction in extent is noted in the coastal dry region between 2010 and 2020 likely owing to lands in development – i.e., large sites initially cleared for new residential areas reverting to grass and shrubland (Koenig et al., 2024).

2.1.2. Condition changes

The EC index changes between 2010 and 2020, although generally negative, are marginal. Mean condition index values for forests range from 0.38 for lowland and intermediate altitude dry forests (codes 221 and 231), which have almost completely disappeared due to historical land use changes (Cheke and Hume, 2008; Koenig et al., 2024), to 0.57 for upland wet forests (243). The condition for the largest forests (222, 223, 233 and 243) has remained relatively stable (Figure 2a.), as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Forest ecosystems spatial distribution and condition index for a. 2010, b. 2020. Source: Authors' elaboration.

In agricultural ecosystems, minor index reductions are noted in lowland moist (422) and wet (423) regions containing large portions of cropland stocks (Figure 2b.; Figure 4). These results are not unexpected since crop systems have not incurred significant compositional changes during the decade and remain dominated by sugarcane (Koenig et al., 2024; Mahadea-Nemdharry, et al., 2025).

Figure 4: Agricultural ecosystems spatial distribution and condition index for a. 2010, b. 2020. Source: Authors' elaboration.

The condition of the largest areas of urban and industrial ecosystems has also remained stable, with more marked increases in the coastal dry (511) and upland wet regions and decreases in lowland wet (523) and intermediate moist (532) regions (Figure 2c.). Higher variations can be observed in smaller urban areas, namely upland dry (541) and high relief regions (551, 553). In these cases, building density is typically low, adjacent natural environment is well-preserved, and built perimeter to built surface area ratios are large causing parameters from surrounding ecosystems to positively affect the condition index. Figure 5 provides a visual illustration of these dynamics.

Figure 5: Urban and industrial ecosystems spatial distribution and condition index for a. 2010, b. 2020. Source: Authors' elaboration.

Ecosystem-specific condition indices were not recalculated for 2050, as the modelled built-up areas (SC1 & SC2) and tree cover (SC2) were assigned mean values from the year 2020 for each variable per ecosystem type. These areas would therefore display mean EC values and cause no change to the 2020 indices. As changes in extent are projected to occur, however, the evolution of ecosystem mosaics is expected to impact land condition that is addressed in the next section.

2.2. Island-wide ecosystem condition based on original pristine state

The above results provide insight into the condition of individual ecosystems by type but do not inform on the overall condition of the island compared to a pristine condition.

Since decision makers within subnational authorities may struggle to grasp the significance of changes for individual ecosystems for their locus of authority or influence – as they will not typically possess the resources for managing specific ecosystems, an aggregate index for entire administrative areas may more readily inform them. Since condition must be determined within biophysically comparable areas, it should still be differentiated and classified to avoid establishing erroneous reference values across the landscape. For this, we assume the pristine state of the island to be entirely forested and refer to land-climate systems as per the above classification to differentiate forest types. As such, the code 11 indicates coastal dry forests, whereas 43 indicates upland wet forests, for example. This segmentation allows an ecologically-sound determination of condition, which is then presented by administrative units for policy planning, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation of interventions.

2.2.1. Representation by land-climate systems

Figure 6 presents extent and condition across land-climate systems for 2010, 2020, and 2050 (SC1 and SC2). Changes in extent reflect changes in ecosystem types constituting the respective land-climate systems and is discussed in section 2.1.1. The condition index, hereafter referred to as ‘land condition’ (to reflect its intended land policy and management use) shows decrease from 2010 to 2020, which is consistent with the results presented above. Strikingly, developments under SC1 and SC2 appear to produce little impact on the 2050 index values.

Figure 6: Extent (bar chart, primary axis) and condition (line chart, secondary axis) by land-climate system type for 2010, 2020, 2050 SC1, and 2050 SC2. Source: Authors' elaboration.

2.2.2. Representation for policy and decision making

Figure 7 (a) presents land condition index values for 2010, 2020 and 2050 scenarios by district - the largest sub-national administrative units for the island of Mauritius - and a ranking of those in descending order of index value using the year 2020 indices (Figure 7 (b)). In terms of condition change, the results strikingly show that Mauritius was already so degraded in 2010 that further landcover change has had a low impact on ecosystem condition by 2020, and in the modelled 2050 scenarios. See Figure S4 in Supplementary Information for raster maps of this index.

Figure 7: (a) Land condition (dimensionless) by district for 2010, 2020, 2050 SC1, and 2050 SC2, (b) ranking of districts by condition in descending order, based on 2020 index values. Source: Author's elaboration.

In terms of administrative areas, the analysis produced counterintuitive results, whereby the northern districts of Pamplemousses and Riviere du Rempart exhibit lower condition values than the highly urbanised districts of Port Louis and Plaines Wilhems that host the near entirety of the conurbation. The former two districts are characterised by a landscape dominated by agricultural landcover, fragmented by towns and transport infrastructure, and with few natural and high-biodiversity areas. In contrast, the latter two districts contain forested mountains and high lands, including nature reserves. Figure 8 displays condition index scores by district for land and the dominant ecosystem groups. While each score is determined independently, their side-by-side visualisation may inform the identification and prioritisation of restoration interventions as discussed in the following section.

Figure 8: Mean land and ecosystem condition scores by district for the years 2010 (a) and 2020 (b). Source: Authors' elaboration.

Further accounting at lower administrative scales has been carried out (see Figures S5 & S6), enabling a ranking of Municipal and Village Council Areas (MVCAs) within districts, where land condition and distinct ecosystem condition accounts (forest, agricultural ecosystems, as well as urban and industrial ecosystems) can support the identification and prioritisation of interventions in view of improving land and ecosystems condition.

3. Discussion

Despite its potential to ground nature-positive governance in ecological evidence, ecosystem accounting has yet to see widespread adoption in environmental and land use policymaking (Virto et al., 2018; Ahlroth et al., 2019; NESCS, 2024). Barriers to uptake include insufficient institutional capacity (UNSC, 2025) and the technical complexity of the accounts themselves, which can limit engagement by non-specialist policymakers (Díaz et al., 2019; Schneider, et al., 2025). This paper responds to both challenges: it provides a reproducible methodological pathway adhering to the SEEA-EA framework (see Methods) and demonstrates how the resulting accounts can directly inform national and sub-national land use governance. Critically, the results are structured to align with the administrative boundaries through which land use decisions are made in Mauritius, offering a direct route from ecological evidence to policy action, and a replicable model for other SIDS and developing countries. The methodological decisions underpinning these results, including ecosystem boundary-setting, condition indicator selection and weighting, and reference value derivation, are detailed in the Methods section and Supplementary Information. The key governance and policy implications are discussed below, as well as future research avenues which may further support land and environmental governance.

3.1. Relevance to policy and decision making

Policy and decision makers typically require synthesised insights – scientific information made accessible, relevant, and actionable – for the formulation of evidenced-based directives (OECD, 2020; Khalid, et al., 2023; Suazo-Galdames, et al., 2025). From these, technical staff can leverage source data, accounts and analyses at the appropriate scales to elaborate more detailed action plans within the relevant administrative boundaries. In this paper, we have presented results at the level of districts, providing a ranking according to their land index score (Figure 7). Such comparative insights readily highlight potential governance-linked opportunities for Mauritius, as district authorities are ultimately those responsible for issuing building and land use permits, the final hurdle in administrative land use change processes (Koenig & Deenapanray, 2024). Further accounting at lower administrative scales has been carried out, enabling a ranking of Municipal and Village Council Areas (MVCAs) within districts, where both land condition and distinct ecosystem condition accounts (forest, agricultural ecosystems, as well as urban and industrial ecosystems) can support the identification and prioritisation of interventions in view of improving land and ecosystems condition. In practical terms, extent and condition maps, charts and tables such as those presented herein can be created by district and MVCAs to inform the relevant authorities on areas of past and potential future degradation. Based on those results, priority areas may be identified and selected interventions delegated to MVCAs following the principle of subsidiarity (Bothe, 1993; Oh-Seng, et al., 2025). As a simplified example, should an MVCA's land condition index be low but forest condition index high, the local authority may identify improvement opportunities in agricultural and urban ecosystems. The maps shown in Supplementary Information (Fig S5 & S6) are proposed as a starting point for such a process. Should technical capacity constrain their ability to conduct analysis and planning, local authorities can rely on the expertise and input of higher authorities, including national government ministries that responsible for land use planning, environmental protection, agriculture and subsidiary agencies (such as those responsible for forestry, national parks and biodiversity), among others.

A notable finding is that the 2050 SC2 scenario, designed to reflect the degraded ecosystem restoration target of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF), does not appear to improve land condition as measured by the index. This result carries direct relevance to the three UN conventions underpinning the SEEA-EA: it suggests that restoration commitments under the CBD may not translate automatically into gains under LDN metrics relevant to the UNCCD and underscores the importance of scenario-based accounting for reconciling these policy objectives.

While reforestation of grass and shrubland is not effective at improving the land condition index under this metric, this result warrants further explanation. Grass and

shrubland – the land cover class targeted for conversion under SC2 – already contributes positively to several condition variables in its current state, including landscape connectivity, soil organic carbon, and, to a lesser extent, above-ground biomass. Converting 30% of this class to forest therefore produces relatively modest gains in the index, because the starting condition of the converted areas is not negligible. A second factor is spatial dilution: localised restoration gains are averaged across ecological units in the land condition index, dampening their apparent effect at the aggregate scale. Critically, SC2 applies restoration opportunistically across accessible lowland moist areas rather than targeting the sites where condition is lowest or connectivity gains would be greatest. A strategically designed restoration programme, prioritising the most degraded sites and enhancing landscape connectivity between existing forest fragments, could be expected to yield more meaningful index improvements than the area-based KMGBF target modelled here. Indeed, the depth of ecological degradation documented across Mauritius represents a structural *opportunity* for condition improvement, provided restoration is spatially optimised. Moreover, restoration can be expected to generate substantial change in ES provision (Koenig, Meisel & Deenapanray, 2026), with attendant implications for climate resilience under the UNFCCC, illustrating why land condition indices and ES assessments must be read in conjunction rather than as substitutes. Future research in this direction is discussed in section 3.3.

3.2. Limitations and error mitigation

This research has demonstrated the operationalisation of the SEEA-EA methodology on EC for the island of Mauritius. Importantly, it has highlighted several challenges and opportunities in data acquisition, analysis, and reporting, and the proposed solutions contribute to the emerging ecosystem accounting literature. Firstly, results were computed using open-source data of varying spatial resolution for different condition variables. Datasets were produced by the same entities and were of consistent spatial resolution for each variable across the temporal range studied here. Owing to a lack of “widely accepted norms or methods for estimating and transparently presenting the uncertainties of ecosystem assessments” (Vári et al., 2024), uncertainty assessment was not performed in the current study. This is not necessarily an immediate limitation since this constraint applies to most results produced in this field (Nicholson Thomas et al., 2025). Nevertheless, error mitigation was achieved through the sourcing of data having undergone rigorous validation or through the application of documented and transparent methodologies (Table 2), where assumptions were explicitly reported (Burgass et al., 2017).

As shown in the sensitivity analysis (Appendix C), locally derived indicators such as HNVFI (compositional state characteristic) and connectivity (landscape characteristic) had distinct effects on the index, thus meaningfully contributing to its quality.

Furthermore, the inclusion of preliminary results on the coverage of a particular Invasive Alien Plant (IAP) as compositional indicator pointed to additional refinement opportunities (see Appendix D). Locally produced and verified data, such as maps of Environmentally Sensitive Areas (ESA), soil types, and IAP coverage from different species may justify the selection of supplemental or alternative indicators to further improve index reliability, similarly to the IPCC tiered-data approach (Rypdal et al., 2006). In addition, while the future landcover changes (2050 scenarios) used in this study are deemed to be conservative, it would be desirable to use national planning maps from the relevant authorities - e.g. maps of settlement boundaries for more comprehensive scenario modelling, and, hence, more accurate ex-ante extent and condition change assessments. Nevertheless, our results demonstrate the use of ecosystem accounting methods for scenario modelling purposes to inform long-term, environmentally-sound land use planning for achieving nature-positive outcomes, which will simultaneously contribute to enhancing climate resilience (Koenig et al., 2026).

As stated in section 4.3, the current study did not model the anticipated impacts of climate change on relevant variables across the island. Here, the state of variables in 2050 assumed a continuation of the 2020 climate regime, which is expected to change as long-term series have shown a decreasing trend in rainfall over the past century (Republic of Mauritius, 2012), with spatial rainfall patterns (Doorga et al., 2025) and precipitation intensity (Seebocus, Lollchund & Bessafi, 2021) observed to change in Mauritius. Climate-related changes were not included here due to the lack of downscaled climate models and vulnerability assessments at the local level, and the unreliability of continental models for oceanic islands. For example, above ground biomass is predicted to decrease globally but may increase in certain African regions and climatic zones (Uribe et al., 2023). With such climate projections available for continental countries, variations due to climate change for the selected indicators would easily enable the modelling of climate impacts combined with those of terrestrial changes in the relevant continental regions, however these cannot be reasonably expected to apply to oceanic islands.

3.3. Future research avenues

In applying the SEEA-EA framework, the next step is to account for ES, which are influenced by the extent and condition of the ecosystems providing them (La Notte et al., 2022; Martini et al., 2024; Seguin et al., 2026). Should ES assessments be performed through the benefits transfer method, which can suffer from several validity issues when ES values are applied across geographies (Newbold et al., 2018; Mandle et al., 2021; Barton et al., 2024), corrections through condition scores may increase their validity (Martini et al., 2024). This research therefore offers promising perspectives for determining the value of ES at the island scale, especially since the Ecosystem Services

Value (ESV) database (Brander et al., 2025) contains little data from SIDS, and local level factors for Mauritius can be drawn from Koenig, Meisel and Deenapanray (2026). National and sub-national ES valuation, built upon the accounts presented here, would further support: (1) nexus analysis linking biodiversity, climate, water and food (Bateman et al., 2024; IPBES, 2024), (2) decision-making on 'critical natural capital' (Ekins et al., 2003; Brand, 2009; Bradley et al., 2026) and ES at risk from land use change, as well as (3) the various economic and financial analyses introduced in section 1.1. The pathway from the accounts produced here to practical financial application involves several steps: ES valuations must be derived from condition scores, as described above; these must then be expressed in monetary terms suitable for integration into corporate natural capital accounting or sovereign risk models; and they must be communicated in formats legible to financial practitioners (Dudley et al., 2025; Ranger, Pasqua & Adam, 2025; Stuchtey and Witter, 2025). Each step builds on the prior one, meaning the extent and condition accounts presented here are not merely a scientific output but the essential first layer of what could become an actionable nature-related financial disclosure framework for Mauritius and, by extension, for other SIDS seeking to engage with existing and emerging global standards such as the SEEA-EA and the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD) (TNFD, 2023).

Going beyond the benefits transfer method, the obtained results may be used for additional analyses in conjunction with specific datasets. For example, the Mauritian government recently released a land drainage masterplan, containing flood hazard maps, showing flood-prone areas, risk zones, no go zones and no expansion zones (Land Drainage Authority, 2025). Future research may establish the influence of land or ecosystem condition on flood risk, enabling a precise quantification of the flood mitigation benefits provided by ecosystems in various watershed settings, and therefore the value of such natural infrastructure (Bedford et al., 2025; Rebalance Earth, 2025; Stuchtey and Witter, 2025). The results of such a study would further reinforce economic and financial models and help in prioritising MVCAs for investments in nature-based solutions for the dual purpose of increasing natural capital and biodiversity and reducing climate vulnerabilities (e.g. due to flooding).

Finally, SIDS and oceanic islands play a crucial role to global sustainability through their support of Ocean ecosystems productivity, namely through coral reefs. As much of the Oceans are oligotrophic, islands provide important nutrient inflows, the quantity and quality of which are dictated by the condition of their terrestrial ecosystems (Sandin et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2023; Allgeier, 2024). Future research may investigate the effect of terrestrial ecosystem condition on coastal and marine ecosystems which are critical to island economics, in the context of climate change and land-based stressors (Doorga et al., 2023).

3.4. Concluding remarks

This study directly addresses a gap identified at the global level: as of 2024, no country classified as a SIDS had produced either extent or condition accounts under the SEEA-EA framework (UN, 2025). By demonstrating a transparent, open-source and replicable accounting pathway applied to the terrestrial ecosystems of Mauritius, this work offers a practical model for other developing countries facing similar constraints of limited land area, high ecological endemism, intense land use pressure, and constrained institutional capacity (Koenig et al., 2026). The accounts reveal that Mauritius was already highly degraded by 2010, such that a decade of subsequent land-cover change produced only marginal shifts in overall condition — a finding with direct implications for prioritising governance action. Counterintuitively, the most degraded administrative districts are not those hosting the urban conurbation, but those dominated by fragmented agricultural landscapes with few high-biodiversity areas, underscoring the value of sub-national disaggregation. The level of spatial and thematic detail attainable within the small geographical extents characteristic of SIDS — including sub-national governance scales, multi-year comparisons, and prospective scenario modelling — demonstrates that the SEEA-EA framework is particularly well suited to such contexts. Strikingly, the 2050 restoration scenario aligned with KMGBF targets does not translate into commensurate gains under LDN metrics, highlighting tensions between the objectives of the CBD and UNCCD that scenario-based accounting is uniquely positioned to reveal. As the international community moves toward integrated reporting across these conventions, ecosystem accounts of this kind position island states to participate meaningfully in, and contribute to, this global agenda.

4. Materials and Methods

4.1. Ecosystem extent

4.1.1. Delineating and classifying ecological units

Mapping ecosystems was undertaken through a downscaled procedure based on Sayre et al. (2020), as shown in Figure 9 for forest ecosystems. The initial step consisted in delineating and classifying ecological units by intersecting climate regions, elevation-landform ranges, watersheds, and landcover data layers. This was followed by correcting the classification in terms of moisture domains through a Median Absolute Deviation (MAD) statistical approach using actual Evapo-Transpiration and Interception (ETIa) data.

Figure 9: Procedure for classification of ecosystem units (forest ecosystems). (1a) Isohyetal map of LTM precipitation (1991-2020), (1b) Digital Elevation Model (DEM), (1c) LC (Koenig et al. 2024), (2a) IPCC climate regions, (2b) Landform, (2c) Primary watersheds, (2d) Forest cover, (3) Intersection of unit boundaries to provide ecological units, (4) Calculation of mean ETIa per ecological unit, (5) Identification of outliers per climate region, (6a) reassignment of climate region to define ecosystem types, (6b) example of reassigned units outside the 2a. climate region boundary. Source: Author's elaboration.

First, climate regions were defined following the approach proposed by Sayre et al. (2020) using the IPCC default climate regions (Bickel et al., 2006). Mauritius belongs to the tropical domain characterised by a Mean Annual Temperature (MAT) exceeding 18°C and ≤ 7 days of frost per year. Climate regions were then defined by altitude and Mean Annual Precipitation (MAP). Areas below 1000m altitude and receiving over 2000mm MAP are termed Tropical Wet, those with $\text{MAP} \leq 2000\text{mm}$ and $> 1000\text{mm}$ Tropical Moist, and $\text{MAP} \leq 1000\text{mm}$ Tropical Dry. Due to its water-stressed status (World Bank, 2016) and for land drainage needs, Mauritius is subject to water resources monitoring and research on an ongoing basis. This makes multiple reports and studies available (Ministry of Energy and Public Utilities, 2005; Dhurmea, Boojhawon, & Rughooputh, 2009; Nel et al., 2012; Fischer et al., 2013; Doorga et al., 2025), including maps of rainfall patterns (isohyetal). In this research, the 1991-2020 Long Term Mean (LTM) isohyetal map by Doorga et al. (2025) was used to infer climate regions as per the above IPCC definition. For this study, climate regions are classed as tropical dry (1), moist (2), and wet (3). The numbering in brackets is later used for coding the three climate regions, which are effectively moisture domains in this case, given the single temperature domain.

Second, an elevation-landform scheme was established from the digital elevation model (Land Drainage Authority, 2025) and relevant literature. Page & D'Argent (1997), cited by Kueffer & Mauremootoo (2004), define lowland forests as occurring below- and upland forests as occurring above- 200-400 meters above sea level (asl). The range (200-400m) is referred to as intermediate altitude. Similarly, an ecogeographic study of *Ipomoea* species in Mauritius defines low altitude as 0-150m, moderate altitude as 150-500m, and high altitude above 500m (Boyjnath et al., 2024). Kueffer & Mauremootoo (2004) also refer to a coastal zone, however its elevation range is unspecified. Indeed, “there is no single definition for the coast and the coastal zone/area, where the latter emphasises the area or extent of the coastal ecosystems” (Wong et al., 2014). In the context of climate-change, the low-elevation coastal zone (LECZ) has been formalised as extending from 0-10m elevation due to the high vulnerability of these areas to inundation and erosion, saltwater intrusion, and storm impacts (McGranahan, Balk, & Anderson, 2007; Wong et al., 2014; Wright et al., 2023). The LECZ has been extended to 20m to support vulnerability assessments in several geographies, including the Pacific Island Countries and Territories (Pacific Data Hub, 2025) and the Mediterranean (Wolff et al., 2018), among others (UNDP, 2018). This threshold has been considered relevant for Mauritius, where the shoreline belt is highly urbanised. In many parts of Mauritius, this urbanisation goes past 20m elevation, and natural habitats “have been destroyed almost completely” (Kueffer & Mauremootoo, 2004) in those built-up belts. The following altitudinal ranges were therefore adopted: 0-20m (coastal), 20-200m (lowland plains), 200-400m (intermediate altitude), and $>400\text{m}$ (uplands), providing an ecologically meaningful framework. Slope analysis then provided the extent of steep

reliefs, namely mountains, gorges and cliffs, which are known to break zonal climate patterns (Mucina et al., 2006; Karagulle et al., 2016; Merritt, 2022). The extent of slopes exceeding 30 degrees was retained as it added a differentiated and localised information layer to the above categories. The combined altitudinal ranges and steep terrain are henceforth referred to as landforms, classed as follows: coastal (1), lowland (2), intermediate (3), upland (4), and relief (5), whereby the numbers in brackets are used as elevation-landform identifiers.

Third, the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) (Land Drainage Authority, 2025) was used to identify watersheds, widely referred to as functional ecological units, as they capture how land, vegetation, soils, and climate interact to regulate nutrient cycling, soil erosion, sediment transport, and other ecological flows (Primack, 2006; Weber, 2014). Finally, specific LC classes were extracted from the landcover maps that are produced by Koenig et al. (2024). In the case of forests, tree-covered areas smaller than 0.5 hectares were excluded for consistency with the FAO's authoritative definition of forests (FAO, 1999). This sieving threshold was also applied to built-up areas for consistency.

Given the smoothed climate region boundaries provided by the isohyetal map (defining precipitation ranges and thus climate regions in the present case), it was anticipated that ecological units may not strictly adhere to the map's limits - i.e. some watershed areas downstream of regions pre-classified as wet, for example, may also be characterised as wet due to biotic and abiotic factors. A classification correction was, therefore, conducted by calculating the mean ETIa by ecological unit, and reclassifying outliers using a threshold of 1.5x MAD from the pre-classified dry, moist and wet groups. The MAD approach was preferred to mean- or standard deviation- based methods, as it better resists the effects of outliers that can disproportionately affect those (Hampel et al., 2005; Rousseeuw & Hubert, 2017). ETIa was chosen in lieu of a more processing intensive use of temperature and moisture data, which would remain imperfect without the inclusion of cloud cover, the effect of trade winds, and shading by relief, among other biotic and abiotic factors. ETIa, therefore, served as a proxy for the above-listed variables, itself being subject to their combined effects. Data was sourced from the FAO Wapor platform (FAO, 2024). Since the assessment of changes or transitions in ecosystem types due to climate change (e.g. tropical moist forest transitioning to tropical dry) was beyond the scope of this research, a 10-year average of ETIa was computed (2011-2020), and the mean was calculated per ecological unit for both 2010 and 2020. Different MAD thresholds were trialled (3.5x, 2.5x, and 1.5x), and mapped results checked against known dry, moist and wet areas. Dr. Vincent Florens, Associate Professor of Ecology at the University of Mauritius, was consulted on the procedure (Florens, 2025), qualifying the results as a suitable working segmentation, which may be subject to validation through geobiological field surveys that are beyond the scope of the present study. The procedure was repeated with the LC classes of cropland and build-up areas.

4.1.2. Final ecosystems typology

The procedure described above enabled the distinction between 15 sub-types per ecosystem group (EG) identified from the three dominant LC classes by extent. These are, therefore, more numerous than the IUCN-GET Ecosystem Functional Groups (EFG) (Keith et al., 2020) relevant to Mauritius. To maintain practicality given their disaggregated character and the small geographical scale of the island, six LC classes were not further differentiated: mangroves, upland and lowland marshes, rivers, water bodies, and sandy beaches. Five LC classes, namely built areas, land in development, transport, quarries and solar farms were aggregated into one EG to match the IUCN-GET urban and industrial ecosystems EFG. These were, however, differentiated by elevation-landform and climate regions as per the above description. The grass & shrubs and golf classes were similarly merged, and Table 1 (Section 2.1) presents the final typology used onwards for Mauritius, as well as its alignment with the IUCN-GET.

4.2. Ecosystem Condition

4.2.1. Condition variables, input data and preprocessing

Condition indices (henceforth referred to as *indices* or *index* for conciseness) were computed for the three largest ecosystem groups described above, namely forests, agricultural ecosystems, and urban & industrial ecosystems, as well as a land index. EC accounts rely on geospatial data, which represent ESC as introduced above. Here, seven variables, with at least one per ESC, were selected following conceptual, practical, and ensemble criteria (Keith et al., 2020; Czúcz et al., 2021). While distinct sets of variables may be applied to different ecosystem types (Maes et al., 2020; UN 2021), the same variables were selected here to compute the index for each ecosystem and land system. This is due to low data availability in Mauritius, as the island is often excluded from continental Africa datasets, and the applicability of these variables to each ecosystem group. Table 2 presents the retained variables, justification, spatial resolution and data sources. When selecting variables, their categorisation per ESC in some cases required a comparative examination of their behaviour across the 2010-2020 period. Total Biomass Production (TBP) and ETIa, for instance, were initially considered as functional and physical state characteristics, respectively. However, they exhibited near-identical changes between the two years when rescaled to 0-1 indicators. ETIa was therefore regarded as a functional state variable and not used in favour of TBP. Evaporation (EV) was instead retained for physical state to ensure parsimony (ensemble criterion).

As datasets were sourced from different providers and were for different spatial resolutions, they were individually reprojected to Mauritius' coordinate reference system (EPSG 32740), clipped by a buffered coastline (1km offset) of the island excluding islets, and then resampled to 10-meter resolution to match LC maps that

were used to derive the connectivity indicator. Datasets for EV, TBP and Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) contained gaps (empty pixels). To fill them, ecosystem maps were vectorised to enable the extraction of mean values for each variable per ecosystem type for 2010 and 2020. Shapefiles were then rasterised, providing complete maps where each pixel value equated to the mean variable value for the corresponding ecosystem. The original data was then superimposed upon these maps by mosaicking so as to reduce analysis errors that would be introduced by data gaps. Such a method draws from the Ecosystem Natural Capital Accounting (ENCA) guidelines (Weber, 2014). For 2010 and 2020, respectively, the errors amounted to 1.9% and 1.6% for EV, 6.6% and 9.5% for TBP, and 1.3% for SOC. This method was also applied to create the two 2050 scenario datasets that are based on 2020 data: ecosystem-specific mean values were applied to new urban and forest areas and corresponding rasters superimposed on 2020 data, assuming no other changes. SAGA software (Conrad et al., 2015) was used for all GIS operations.

Table 2: Selected ecosystem condition variables. Source: Author's elaboration.

Ecosystem state characteristic	Variable and unit	Description and justification	Resolution (meters)	Data source
Physical state	Evaporation (EV) mm/yr	Physical state characteristics are descriptors of abiotic components, including soil structure, imperviousness, and water availability (UN 2021). As described below, Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) was used as chemical state characteristic which will be dependent on artificial areas based on LC, and Total Biomass Production (TBP) as functional state characteristic which is dependent on (and therefore partly expresses-) water availability. Whereas precipitation data is available from the CHIRPS dataset (Funk et al., 2015) as a measure of water input, its 5km resolution is low and thus unsuitable for our application. The evaporation variable (FAO, 2018) was instead chosen, as it expresses spatial distribution of water abundance in the landscape. It is also distinct from evapotranspiration, which was found to be closely related to Total Biomass Production (TBP) and was therefore seen as a functional state indicator.	250m	FAO WaPOR platform (FAO, 2024)
Chemical state	Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) at 100cm depth, t/ha	While SOC at low depths may be considered to express the organic productivity of soils as a functional characteristic, data are often lacking on wide temporal ranges. Instead, SOC at 100cm depth (Hengl et al., 2017) has been retained as a chemical state characteristic. The latest available data values (year 2017) were assumed as fixed between 2010 and 2050 and use LC maps to assign SOC values of zero for artificial areas, since SOC at this depth is either released through earthworks for construction, sealed by impervious surfaces, or generally unavailable to biotic ecosystem processes.	250m	ISRIC Data Hub (ISRIC, 2024)
Compositional state	High Natural Value Index (HNVI), unitless	The SEEA-EA does not consider indicators of protection status as appropriate measures for condition because, "an ecosystem could be protected and nevertheless be in poor condition" (UN 2021). In many cases, however, such indicators represent the only available information on high biodiversity areas. Mauritius has produced maps of "environmentally sensitive areas" (ESA) to be protected as referenced in its National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (Republic of Mauritius, 2017b). However, these were never officially published (see Chapter 2), and thus unavailable for this study. In 2021, the Critical Ecosystem Partnership Fund (CEPF) commissioned an update of its "ecosystem profile" for the Madagascar and Indian Ocean Islands (MADIO) biodiversity hotspot, which identified and	10m	CEPF (2022)

		ranked Key Biodiversity Areas (KBA) per country (CEPF, 2022). This exercise was conducted by experts and consultants with the support of local stakeholders including authorities and yielded a map of high and low investment priority areas, including protected zones such as the National Park and some mountain reserves. Broader areas with no specific protection status were also identified as KBAs. The boundaries of these areas were accessible as Keyhole Markup Language (KML) files on the CEPF website. A value of 0 was assigned to areas not classified as KBA, 0.5 to low-priority areas, and 0.75 was assigned to high-priority areas. 0.75 was chosen instead of 1 as high-priority KBAs are vast, while areas of intact biodiversity are nearly absent on the island.		
	Invasive Alien Plants (IAP) coverage	IAPs are one of the global threats to biodiversity (IPBES, 2019), including Mauritius which has developed an Invasive Alien Species (IAS) strategy (Government of Mauritius, 2008). As such, their extent is a good compositional variable indicating forest ecosystems degradation. This indicator represented expanses of <i>Ravenala madagascariensis</i> , an IAS identifiable by its distinct shape from high-resolution satellite images (Carpouren et al., 2023). This was used here for demonstration purposes, as mapping was conducted through SAGA's Random Forest classifier using 2020 geomedian multispectral images, without ground-truthing.	10m	Digital Earth Africa (DEA, 2021)
Structural state	Above-Ground Biomass (AGB), Mg/ha	AGB data are widely used and recommended as a measure of ecosystem structural state (Santoro & Cartus, 2023).	100m	ESA-CCI database (ESA-CCI, 2024)
Functional state	Total Biomass Production (TBP), kg/ha	TBP is an expression of Net Primary Production (NPP), a descriptor of the ecosystem function. Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) can be used as a surrogate for NPP (UNSD, 2020). However, FAO/WaPOR provides an annual TBP dataset that was retained here (FAO, 2018). Actual Evapotranspiration and Interception (ETIa) was another potential functional state variable. When rescaled to a 0-1 indicator for 2010 and 2020, however, its magnitude and changes closely matched those of TBP and was deemed redundant.	250m	FAO WaPOR platform (FAO, 2024)
Landscape characteristic	Connectivity, unitless	As a landscape characteristic, a fragmentation index was computed through the size of the effective mesh (Jaeger, 2000), derived from LC maps and additional road data from Open Street Map (OSM, 2024). Here, built-up areas, transport infrastructure, and quarries were considered as fragmenting elements, while the remaining classes were assumed to be natural or semi-natural areas. Cropland, for instance, is largely free of human traffic and light	10m	Land Cover (Chapter 3), Open Street Map (OSM, 2024)

pollution, is used by fauna and soil organisms, enables water infiltration, etc. Fragmenting elements were converted to no-data, whereas natural elements comprised the remaining data. Patches were then converted to vector files and intersected with the boundaries of primary watersheds to produce the mesh against which fragmentation is calculated. Although based on fragmentation, high index values express low fragmentation and thus high connectivity. The indicator is thus referred to as connectivity for directionality. Notably, a value of 0 is given to urban & industrial ecosystems, which are fragmenting elements by definition.

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4.2.2. Rescaling and indexing

Once the data were pre-processed as described above, minimum and maximum values were extracted for variables with physical units (EV, SOC, AGB, and TBP), for each ecosystem type within the forests, agricultural and urban & industrial groups, and for land system types. These (minima and maxima) served as reference values to rescale the respective datasets from their native units into unitless indicators in a 0-1 range – i.e. Min-Max normalisation. Reference values for long-term stock variables SOC and AGB were taken across 2010 and 2020 (meaning that if the minimum was in 2010 and the maximum in 2020, for example, these were selected), whereas to rescale those potentially exhibiting large climate related year-on-year variability; EV and TBP, minima and maxima were taken for each year. Rescaling followed equation (1), where I is the indicator value, V the variable value, V_L the lower reference value, and V_H the higher reference value (UN, 2021; Martini et al., 2024).

$$I = \frac{(V - V_L)}{(V_H - V_L)} \quad (1)$$

The procedure was performed sequentially as follows:

- a) Minima and maxima (reference values) were extracted from raster data to ecosystem shapefiles via SAGA's "grid statistics for polygons" tool. Lookup tables were generated for reference values (Appendix A, Tables S1-S4);
- b) Raster data were clipped by ecosystem shapefiles;
- c) Rescaling was done via the SAGA grid-calculator tool, using equation 1 referring to lookup tables for V_L and V_H ;
- d) Output rasters were re-assembled by individual ecosystem groups and separately for land systems, i.e. the island as a whole.

Steps (b) and (c) demanded a high number of operations: repeated for two years (2010 and 2020), four variables, and 60 distinct classes – 15 subtypes for four groups, namely forests, croplands, urban & industrial ecosystems, and land-climate systems. To mitigate potential errors in the successive manual selection of files and directories (raster data, shapefiles, lookup table, output directory) through the SAGA graphical user interface, a Python script was written to automate steps (b) and (c) (script provided in Appendix B). Steps (a) and (d) were performed manually to enable control and verification of intermediate and final outputs. HVNI, IAP coverage and connectivity indicators are unitless and did not require rescaling. For HVNI, although only three values were possible across the landscape, i.e., 0; 0.5, and 0.75, the maximum was maintained as 1, representing a pristine condition which no longer exists. For the two 2050 scenarios, the procedure was applied to the land index only; producing indices for ecosystems was not deemed relevant since new built-up and tree-covered areas were

given average values. Land index results were anticipated to provide more insights to land use policy, given that administrative areas include different ecosystem types.

Next, composite ecosystem indices were computed from the condition indicators by assigning a weight to each indicator, whereby the sum of weights amounting to 1. Hence, the composite index was given by the sum of weighted indicators. Indices were initially calculated with all but the IAP coverage indicator. As the indicator typically not recommended by the SEEA-EA framework (see Table 2), HVNI was given a weight of 0.1 while the remainder were each given an equal weight of 0.18.

4.2.3. Notes on reference values and indicator weights

The selection of reference values and indicator weights are critical issues that have been well addressed in the recent EC literature (Keith et al., 2020; Czúcz et al., 2021; Nicholson Thomas et al., 2025). In this paper, reference values were taken as minimum and maximum pixel values for each variable per ecosystem. This may be considered a contemporary approach (UN, 2021; Usubiaga-Liaño, Selomane & Comte, 2025), meaning the reference condition will only reflect the current highest condition, or the highest condition present across the study's timeframe. For forest ecosystems, selected maximum values may pertain to the 1.3 percent remnants of indigenous forests (CEPF, 2022) and may thus be close to pristine condition, whereas for urban and industrial ecosystems, the upper reference value may reflect those of urban nature, such as parks or urban-riparian areas. This approach contributed to relatively low index values in agricultural and urban ecosystems, likely because maximum values pertained to isolated high value areas for several indicators. Rescaling could, therefore, be conducted using the 95th percentile (or lower) as maximum to avoid outliers (Lecomte, Aubard & Roche, 2024). Results nevertheless remain normative and pertinent for spatial comparisons within ETs. Interestingly, the proposed land index mitigates the potential ambiguities of reference value selection by retaining minima and maxima by land-climate system regardless of ecosystems, thereby providing a normative condition scale relevant to LDN (UNSD, 2020). In this case, all land condition is rescaled according to the would-be pristine state as the highest contemporary condition, which was deemed appropriate for Mauritius where the original landcover was almost entirely forest (Baker, 1877; Cheke and Hume, 2008). Biasing factors may however persist – e.g. data for mangroves would not be appropriate for setting reference values across coastal areas that may not ecologically and geomorphologically support mangroves. As such, the above restriction of minima and maxima to a suitable percentile may mitigate this issue.

Regarding indicator weights, the adopted scheme aimed at giving equal value to each ecosystem state characteristic in the index. This was despite HVNI being considered a weak indicator as per SEEA-EA guidelines (UN, 2021; Vári et al., 2024). Notably, low index values for agricultural and urban ecosystems can be partly attributed to their

HVNI value of zero, and a connectivity value of zero for urban ecosystems as these indicators were still given a weight in the index calculations for these ecosystems. The issue here is that if these indicators would be excluded from the calculation of the composite index, the index range would increase, which would give a false impression of high condition relative to other ecosystems for account users not familiar with the methodology. Overall, weights may be changed according to policy priorities (Vári et al., 2024; Czúcz et al., 2025); whether focused on biodiversity, in which case additional compositional indicators are recommended, or carbon sequestration for example. The latter case may however not be particularly meaningful in the case of Mauritius (and SIDS in general), where land-based carbon is low compared to national emissions (Doorga et al., 2023). The contribution of EC to ES may also justify a higher weight being placed on certain variables (Kervinio, Surun, Comte, & Levrel, 2023; Martini et al., 2024), depending on national circumstances or policy needs. Nevertheless, care must be exercised so that composite indices that are produced to support policy orientations are aligned with the overall objectives of UN conventions and their objectives, as referred to in the introduction.

4.2.4. Sensitivity analysis

For the purpose of describing the effect of individual indicators on the index, a sensitivity analysis was conducted whereby the weight of each indicator was successively reduced to 0.05, while others were given an equal weight of 0.19 (see Appendix C). This was constrained to the land condition for 2020 only, as it was considered the most relevant to policy and captured the entire island. Once the above was completed in accordance with the SEEA-EA guideline, the potential impact of IAP coverage was tested by including the indicator in the land condition index. In this case, indicator weights were modified to 0.16 for EV, SOC, AGB, and TBP; 0.15 for IAP, and 0.05 for HVNI (see results in Appendix D). Since each indicator was shown to have a distinct effect on condition, thus satisfying the parsimony guideline (Czúcz et al., 2021), lower and upper bound indices were not produced as these would simply equate to reducing the importance of indicators positively or negatively in the final index.

4.3. 2050 scenarios

In addition to accounting for 2010 and 2020, two 2050 LC scenarios were built from the 2020 map from Koenig et al. (2024). The two scenarios were defined as follows:

- **Scenario 1 (SC1):** SC1 reflects the planned land use policy or business-as-usual (BAU) scenario. It is used as the reference scenario for investigating policy-induced changes as captured in Scenario 2 (SC2). Under SC1, in 2050, all areas previously classified as “land in development” were assumed to have become built-up, and 15 of the smart-city projects currently listed by the Economic Development Board (EDB, 2025) have been built. To reflect these on a SC1 (2050)

land cover map, QGIS (QGIS.org, 2024) was used to georeference the proposed projects' masterplans obtained from their respective websites or publicly available documentation (see Appendix E). Georeferenced masterplans were then reclassified using the above typology (LC classes) and added to the 2020 LC map. Large infrastructure constructions visible from current Google Earth imagery, such as new primary roads were also added. No other changes to the 2020 LC were assumed. Given the financial maximisation paradigm that underpins the governance of land use in Mauritius (Koenig & Deenapanray, 2024), the land use changes in favour of 'built-up' LC accounted for under SC1 are, therefore, taken to be conservative. Nevertheless, SC1 serves to illustrate a likely trajectory of change to 2050.

- **Scenario 2 (SC2):** As SC1 essentially consists of urban sprawl and new infrastructure that are expected to result in ecosystem degradation, a restoration scenario (SC2) was conceived in alignment with the targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF). Target 2 for 2030 is to ensure that by 2030 at least 30 per cent of areas of degraded terrestrial [...] ecosystems are under effective restoration (CBD, 2022). For the present purposes, the "grass and shrubs" LC type was considered as a degraded ecosystem, knowing that Mauritius was historically entirely covered with forest (Baker, 1877; Cheke & Hume, 2008). Thirty percent (30%) of the 2020 grass and shrubs area (61km²) was thus converted to tree cover to represent KMGBF-aligned ecosystem restoration. As such, SC2 adds a 'restoration of degraded land' component to SC1. Figure E1 in Appendix E shows the spatial extent of land cover changes for SC1 and SC2.

SC1 was elaborated in alignment with the provisions of the draft National Land Development Strategy (NLDS), which stated that there is no demand for further major urban expansion beyond the planned strategic growth areas that smart city projects represent (Republic of Mauritius, 2021). This statement is notably absent from the newly adopted National Development Strategy (NDS), which identifies a need for affordable housing, to be met by the provision of 12,000 units across the island (MHL, 2025), thus supporting the conservativeness of SC1. On ecosystem restoration, the draft NLDS had made provision for "Green/Blue corridors", forming three distinct bands from the East to West coasts of the island. The such proposed corridors would have been implemented through greening of hard infrastructure (highways, cycleways, footpath), and nature-based infrastructure, including river valleys, and rivulets and streams, among others (Republic of Mauritius, 2021). This policy direction is less prominent in the adopted NDS (MHL, 2025), with the figure representing East-West corridors in the draft NLDS no longer present. In addition, upon observation of satellite imagery, it was noted that agriculture is currently prevalent in the areas initially shown,

thus raising several concerns with respect to food security, and land tenure. SC2 was therefore aligned with the island's Protected Area Network Expansion Strategy (PANES), which may present economic opportunities through agroforestry, carbon sequestration, biodiversity and social co-benefits (IPBES, 2024; Bateman et al., 2024). In line with limiting the scope of the present study to the application of the SESA-EA, the economics and political economy of restoring the 61km² of degraded land were not accounted for here. SC2 primarily serves in the modelling of ecosystem condition and illustrates the distribution of potential restoration areas.

To obtain ecosystem extent and condition from the 2050 landcover maps, the procedures described in the above sections (4.1, 4.2) were applied with 2020 data, assuming no other changes to condition variables other than those associated with modelled LC changes. The implications of this assumption with respect to climate change are discussed in section 3.2.

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